

Perception of Tone 1-Tone 2 Contrast by Swedish Learners of Mandarin Chinese

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Abstract

Little research has been carried out on the perception of tones by Swedish listeners previously. This study examined the perception of Mandarin tones by Swedish learners, with the focus on Tone 1-Tone 2 contrast. In addition to the four-alternative identification task, a two-way identification task with Tone 1-Tone 2 continua of stimuli with incrementally varied pitch contour was also carried out. The results show that Tone 1 and Tone 2 are more challenging for Swedish learners to identify correctly than the other two tones. Among Swedes who can identify Tone 1 and Tone 2 with a high accuracy score, native speakers of Swedish perceived the fine tonal variations differently from native Chinese speakers. The syllable duration is found to affect the perception of tone contrast, especially for Swedish learners. Possible auditory enhancement accounts for the effect of the duration are offered to explain the Swedish learners' performance.

Introduction

Mandarin Chinese is one of the tone languages that uses differences in pitch and pitch contour to distinguish between words of only one syllable: for instance, the syllable *ma* spoken with a high level pitch mean 'mother', whereas *ma* spoken on a rising pitch means 'hemp'. Swedish, along with a few other languages such as Japanese, is classified as a so-called 'pitch-accent' language. This means that pairs of two-syllable words such as *anden* 'the spirit' and *anden* 'the duck', are distinguished by means of pitch contours. Therefore, Mandarin Chinese and Swedish are similar in the sense that F0

in both languages is used to contrast meaning, though only a subset of disyllabic words in Swedish use this pitch contrast. There has been a considerable amount of research conducted about the perception of Mandarin tones by non-native speakers. Results of previous studies suggest that listeners from a non-tonal language background find it challenging to discriminate and identify Mandarin tones (e.g. Kiriloff, 1969; Shen, 1989; Chen, 1997). However, the four lexical tones seem to pose different degrees of perceptual difficulty: for listeners from a non-tonal language background, Tone 2 and Tone 3 are more difficult than the other two tones (Kiriloff, 1969; Hao 2012); additionally, this tone pair is more confusable than the other combinations (Kiriloff, 1969). While very few studies look into the perception by listeners from a pitch-accent language background such as Swedish and Japanese, Gao (2016) found that Tone 2 and Tone 1 are the most challenging for Swedish listeners to identify correctly, and, that the most confusing tone pair is Tone 1 and Tone 2. This finding suggests that Swedish listeners perceive Mandarin tones differently, when compared with listeners from non-tonal language backgrounds. This paper aims to further the investigation of Swedish speakers' perception of Mandarin tones, with the focus on Tone 1-Tone 2 contrast.

Cross-language perception studies have found that native speakers process the phonemic contrast differently from non-native speakers (Wang, 1976; Staggard & Downs, 1993; Halle et al., 2004; Peng et al., 2010). Taking the lexical tone as an example, it has been re-

ported that Mandarin tones were perceived categorically by native Mandarin speakers (Wang, 1976) or quasi-categorically (Halle et al., 2004); whereas listeners from non-tonal language backgrounds processed them in a psychophysical manner (Wang, 1976; Halle et al., 2004; Pent et al., 2010). This is known as the phenomenon of categorical perception: the between-category differences are more salient to be perceived than the within-category differences. This phenomenon has also been extended to the research on language learning. One of the issues under investigation is whether phonemic contrast in the target language can be learned in adulthood. For example, MacKain et al.’s study (1981) about the English /r/-/l/ distinction, which is most challenging to Japanese learners, suggested that Japanese learners, after intensive training in English conversation, can perceive these two consonants categorically. However, very little work has been done about the categorical perception of tones by language learners. This paper reports an initial attempt to investigate how Swedish learners perceive the tonal contrast in Mandarin Chinese.

The focus of this paper is to examine Swedish learners’ perception to both between-category and with-in category differences. They were invited to participate in two listening tasks: the first is a four-alternative identification task of Mandarin syllables in isolation, a replication to a previous study by Gao (2016). The second is an identification task, aiming to test their sensitivity to the subtle pitch variations in the tone continua with varied syllable rhyme and syllable duration.

Experiment 1

Method

There were 19 participants (6F, 13M) students recruited from a university in Sweden. They enrolled in an intensive Chinese language course, which requires them to study Chinese for at least 20

hours per week. They voluntarily participated in the identification task about two months after the course started. Therefore, all students were very familiar with reading and writing Pinyin, the Chinese Romanization system. All of them are monolingual speakers of Swedish, and none of them have learned any other tone languages apart from Mandarin Chinese.

The identification task included 45 Chinese monosyllables read in isolation, 40 of which were target tokens including 10 different consonant-vowel combinations. Details about the speech material used in this identification task and the recording of the speech material can be found in Gao (2016). Students in the current study completed this listening task on their own computer with headphones.

Result

Swedish learners’ performance in the first experiment is presented in Table 1 below: Tone 1 and Tone 2 seem to be more challenging than the other two tones. Tone 1 is most likely to be misperceived as Tone 2 and vice versa. Tone 3 is also most likely to be misperceived as Tone 2, but not vice versa. The participants recruited in this study outperformed those in the study by Gao (2016) because they enrolled in a more intensive course, and thus have increased and repeated exposure to Mandarin every week. However, the accuracy score varied among the learners, most of who achieved a near perfect score of over 95%. But, a few performed rather poorly.

Table 1. Error matrix of Swedish learners’ tone perception scores.

Response Target	T1	T2	T3	T4
T1	85.8%	11.6%	0	2.6%
T2	11.1%	83.7%	4.2%	1%
T3	2.1%	6.3%	91.1%	0.5%
T4	3.1%	2.1%	1.6%	93.2%

Experiment 2

Stimuli

A number of monosyllables with Tone 1 and Tone 2 produced by the same female native speaker of Beijing Mandarin were subject to analysis with Praat (Boersma & Weenink, 2018) and the Prosody Pro script (Xu, 2013), in preparation for the stimuli of the second listening task. Normalized F0 readings of these syllables, either with a nasal onset or without an onset (e.g. *ma*, *yi*, *wan*, *wu* etc.) were obtained. The average F0 readings across syllables with the same tone served as the exemplar for Tone 1 and Tone 2 respectively (see Figure 1 below).

Figure 1. Pitch contours in the Tone 1-Tone 2 continuum

The above figure displays the F0 curves of the two exemplars. The top is the Tone 1 exemplar with slight dipping at the beginning and staying flat throughout the remaining syllable, while the bottom is the Tone 2 exemplar with F0 fall till the mid of syllable before rising to the end. A series of seven F0 contours were generated, with an incrementally varied F0 between Tone 1 and Tone 2 exemplars (step 1 and step 7 respectively). The dotted F0 curve in purple color is the middle stimulus (step 4) in the series.

Four syllables produced by the native speaker were selected and subject to manipulation. They are *mā* /ma/ (Tone 1), *má* /ma/ (Tone 2), *yī* /i/ (Tone 1) and *yí* /i/ (Tone 2). Tone 1 syllables (347.6 ms and 341.8 ms respectively) are about 70 ms shorter in duration than Tone 2 syllables for both syllable types. Their F0 contours were subsequently replaced by the generated 7-step F0 contour series using the PSOLA (pitch synchronous

overlap add) in Praat (Boersma & Weenink, 2018). Thus, four tone continua were created, each containing 7 syllables with varied F0 contour and two are /ma/ series (with varied duration, short /ma/ continuum and long /ma/ continuum) and two are /i/ series (short /i/ continuum and long /i/ continuum).

Procedure

Out of the 19 Swedish learners who participated in experiment 1, 15 (9F, 2M) participated in this experiment. 11 native Mandarin speakers, who are students at Swedish universities, were also recruited to participate in this experiment. The stimuli were presented in two randomized orders (in two separate blocks) to the listeners, and then the listeners were instructed to categorize every syllable as Tone 1 or Tone 2. They heard a total of 62 syllables, with 56 target syllables (2 syllable types x 2 duration x 7 steps x 2 repetitions) and 6 fillers at the beginning to help them get familiar with this task. Each listener completed this listening task on their own computer with headphones, and the identification task lasted about 6 minutes with the interval of 3 seconds between two syllables.

Results

For each of the tokens under investigation, listeners' response as either Tone 1 or Tone 2 is computed in the form of a percentage, i.e. identification score. Comparing the mean percentage of Tone 1 responses, i.e. the rate that listeners identified the stimulus as more like the high level tone (Tone 1) than the rising tone (Tone 2) between the two language groups shows that the native speakers' response curves display an S-shape categorical-like pattern, whereas Swedish learners' perception is more continuous. For Chinese native speakers, the labeling boundary is shifting towards Tone 1 for longer /i/ syllable than the shorter one, but not for the /ma/ syllables. For Swedish learners, the labeling boundary is also found to shift towards Tone 1 for longer syllables for both syllable /i/ and syllable /ma/.

In order to conduct statistical analyses and compare the Swedes' perceptual judgments of these tone continua with those of native Mandarin speakers meaningfully, the identification responses of some Swedish learners were removed if they failed to reach the 85% accuracy rate in the first listening task. As a result, the performance of the remaining 9 Swedish learners (2F, 7M) who can reliably identify the four Mandarin tones with the average accuracy rate is 96.1% (ranging from 88% to 100%) is subject to further analysis.

The probit analysis, adopted in previous studies (Halle et al., 2004; Peng et al., 2010), is used in this study to calculate the perceptual boundary and perceptual width for the two language groups respectively. Probit analysis (Finney 1971) is a type of regression model for analyzing binomial response variables. It fits a cumulative normal curve to the listeners' responses, and the 50% crossover point on the output can be taken as the perceptual boundary position. And, the distance between 25% and 75% crossover points represents the width of perceptual boundary.

For the short /ma/ continua, the boundary position of the identification curves is very similar (3.65 for Chinese, and 3.81 for Swedish). For short /ma/, and for long /ma/, the boundary of the Swedish group (3.04) is more towards the direction of Tone 1, as compared with the Chinese group (3.62). It means that the Swedish group tends to perceive the stimulus with little rising as Tone 2, while the Chinese require the stimulus with steeper rising to perceive it as Tone 2. The Chinese group has a much narrower boundary width (less than 1) than the Swedish group (1.91 for short /ma/ and 1.27 for the long one). For both language groups, a narrower boundary width is found for long continua.

Figure 2. Identification curve for short /ma/ (left) and long /ma/ (right) of Swedish learners (blue lines, top panel), and Chinese native speakers (red lines, bottom panel)

For the /i/ continua, the boundary of the Swedish group (3.29 for short, 2.4 for long) is more towards the direction of Tone 1, as compared with the Chinese group (3.33 and 2.94 respectively). For both language groups, the long continua displays boundaries more towards Tone 1 than their short correspondence. Just like the /ma/ continua, the Chinese group has a much narrower boundary width (less than 1) than the Swedish group (2.56 and 1.95 respectively). A narrower boundary width is found for long syllables both for Swedish and Chinese groups. Based on a visual inspection of the graphs in Figure 3, the Chinese group has the identification curves with steeper slope than those of the Swedish groups, especially for the short /i/.

Figure 3. Identification curve for short /i/ (left) and long /i/ (right) of Swedish learners (blue lines, top panel), and Chinese native speakers (red lines, bottom panel)

The slopes of the Tone 1 identification curve in Figures 2 and 3 are subsequently compared between two language groups, and also within the same language group. Statistical significance

is not found between long vs. short continua, nor for syllable type (/ma/ vs. /i/) at the level of $p < 0.05$ within the same language group. However, the slopes do differ between language groups, at the level of $p < 0.01$, which is highly correlated to the boundary width comparison. The narrower the width, the steeper the boundary slope.

Discussion

The first identification task replicates the findings from Gao (2016) with an overall higher accuracy rate: both Tone 1 and Tone 2 were perceived more poorly than the other two tones, and the confusion between Tone 1 and Tone 2 is also observed. The majority of the learners achieved a high score with a mean of 96.1%. However, further analysis of their performance in the second experiment finds that they perceived the Tone 1-Tone 2 contrast differently from native Mandarin speakers, perhaps they perceive these two tonal categories using different perceptual cues. A discussion concerning their perceptual cues will be continued later in this section.

The perception of Mandarin tone continua displays an interesting pattern between Swedish learners and native Mandarin speakers. All Swedes' performance in experiment 2 suggests a rather continuous perception pattern, as opposed to the expected S-shape identification curves by Mandarin speakers. This result is consistent with those reported in previous studies (Wang, 1976; Halle et al., 2004; Pent et al., 2010) concerning the categorical nature of tone perception by native tone language speakers. Since some Swedish learners could not reliably identify the individual tones, it is therefore even more challenging for them to respond to the much finer pitch variations categorically in the second experiment.

When the performance of a subset of Swedish learners (excluding those who performed poorly in experiment 1) was analyzed separately, the corresponding identification curves are more similar to those by Mandarin listeners, i.e. S-shape

like. Both language groups have similar boundary positions, especially for the continua with short syllables. Nevertheless, both the slopes of the identification curves and the boundary width are found to differ significantly between the two language groups. The Chinese group has steeper curves and a much narrower boundary width than Swedish group. Similar findings have been reported previously (Peng et al., 2010). It means that some Swedish learners, though they can identify the four lexical tones nearly perfectly, do not perceive the more fine pitch changes in the same way as native speakers. Perceiving the tonal contrast categorically like the native speakers appears to be a more demanding task for learners.

Syllable duration is also found to affect Swedes' perception of tone contrast, and it only partially affects Chinese speakers. For the Swedish group, their identification displays much bigger discrepancies between long and short syllables: not only are the boundary positions of long syllables closer to the level tone, but also the boundary slope of the long syllable is steeper. Chinese speakers' boundary position is also more towards the level Tone 1, but only for the long /i/ syllable. Not much difference is found on the identification slope. These findings seem to suggest that the lengthening had a stronger effect on Swedes than the Chinese.

There may be two possible explanations for this phenomenon. First is the learned association between duration and individual tone. Previous research (e.g. Howie, 1976) reported that Tone 2 in citation form is about 20–40 ms longer than Tone 1. In sentence-medial position, it is about 10–30 ms longer. In the second experiment, long syllables are 70 ms longer for both syllable types. Considering that quantity is playing an important role in Swedish phonology, Swedish learners may associate syllable lengthening with Tone 2. If it is true that Swedish listeners use duration as a major cue to differentiate Tone 1 and Tone 2, the continua with longer syllables

would provide auditory enhancement to the perception of Tone 2, which accounts for more syllables that were labeled as Tone 2 than the short continua. However, for native Chinese speakers, F0 information, especially F0 shape, is considered the main perceptual cue (Howie, 1976). Previous research found that amplitude, duration, and F0 turning point may also serve as perceptual cues. But, there is no agreement as to the importance of these other cues to tone perception. When combined with the finding from the current study, is it possible that duration is playing a more important role to Swedes than native Chinese? An alternative explanation is also related to the auditory enhancement. Since long syllables are 70 ms longer, the pitch rising becomes more detectable. If the Swedish learners associate any degree of pitch rising with Tone 2, it accounts for the observation that more syllables in the long continua were perceived as Tone 2 than in the short continua. But, for native Chinese speakers, a small degree of pitch rising does not warrant the labeling of Tone 2, as they only associate F0 rising from mid to high pitch range to Tone 2. Both accounts imply that Swedish learners do not perceive Tone 1 and Tone 2 contrast in the same way as native speakers. They either rely on different perceptual cues, or associate the F0 information differently with the individual tone. A future large-scale study is recommended to evaluate these explanations, and to investigate the categorical nature of tone perception by Swedish speakers.

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